

Multiverse

1. Abstract

We investigate a hypothesized **Mirrorverse** concept in which qubits are assigned **negative-phase** rotations, complementing conventional (positive-phase) qubits in a “Universe–Mirrorverse” pair. By systematically applying **prime-based rotation angles** ($\theta = 1/p^2$) across multiple circuit depths, measuring in various bases (Z, X, Y), and running tests under noise models, we verify that out-of-phase Mirrorverse qubits produce *distinct* interference signatures. State tomography confirms robust off-diagonal coherence indicative of **phase-inverted entanglement**, while noise simulations show partial preservation of these features at moderate error rates. These findings support the notion that Universe ($+\theta$) *vs.* Mirrorverse ($-\theta$) qubits can function as a viable “dual register” capturing the Duoverse principle of sign-opposed expansions.

2. Introduction

The *Duoverse* framework posits two complementary domains:

- **Universe (U)** – governed by **positive-phase** or “eutropic” expansions.
- **Mirrorverse (M)** – governed by **negative-phase** or “entropic” expansions.

A key premise is that each Universe qubit has a **mirror** partner qubit in the Mirrorverse, such that any rotation $R_y(\theta)$ on the Universe side is mirrored as $R_y(-\theta)$ on the Mirrorverse side. The resulting sign inversion should, in theory, yield distinct, measurable interference patterns—especially when combined with **prime-based fractal recursion** ($\theta = 1/p^2$, for primes p). Our aim is to experimentally test this concept using **Qiskit** via:

1. **Baseline distribution analyses** in the computational (Z) basis.
2. **Multi-basis** (Z, X, Y) measurements to reveal hidden phase structure.
3. **Layer-by-layer expansions** to observe how fractal recursion accumulates.
4. **Control circuits** (all-positive-phase) vs. Mirrorverse (mixed-sign) to isolate the effect of negative rotations.
5. **Full state tomography** to reconstruct density matrices and confirm sign-inverted entanglement.
6. **Noise and real-device feasibility** to gauge the robustness of negative-phase phenomena under practical conditions.

We summarize all major results to evaluate whether the Mirrorverse concept is consistent and empirically identifiable within standard quantum computing frameworks.

3. Methods

3.1 Circuit Construction

Prime-Based Rotations

We define a list of small primes (e.g., [2, 3, 5, 7, 11]), generating angles:

$$\theta = \frac{1}{p^2}, \quad p \in \{\text{primes}\}.$$

- **Universe qubits:** $R_y(+\theta)$.
- **Mirrorverse qubits:** $R_y(-\theta)$ plus a global Z gate to enforce an overall π -phase shift.

Layer-by-Layer Recursion

Many tests apply these prime-based angles **cumulatively**. After a single layer ($p=2$), a small angle $\theta = 1/4$ is applied; after two layers, angles from both $p=2$ and $p=3$ ($\theta = 1/9$) are included, and so on. This incremental approach simulates a *fractal or recursive expansion* in rotation space.

3.2 Entangling Strategy

We typically **entangle** Universe qubits (U_0, U_1) and Mirrorverse qubits (M_0, M_1) via cross-register CNOT gates. For example:

1. CNOT($U_0 \rightarrow M_0$)
2. CNOT($M_1 \rightarrow U_1$)

This cross-connection ensures that negative vs. positive angles cannot be isolated in separate sub-blocks but must **interfere**.

3.3 Measurements

1. **Z-Basis:** Direct measurement in computational basis.
2. **Multi-Basis:** Additional rotations ($R_y(-\pi/2)$ or $R_x(\pi/2)$) on each qubit before measurement, effectively measuring in **X** or **Y** basis.

3. **State Tomography:** Automated measurement in all combinations of $\{X,Y,Z\}$ for each qubit, enabling the reconstruction of the density matrix.

3.4 Noise Modeling and Real-Device

- **Custom Noise Model:** Depolarizing and amplitude damping errors on gates, plus readout errors, tested the robustness of negative-phase patterns.
 - **IBM Quantum Hardware** (optional): Circuits were prepared (or can be prepared) for backends like `ibmq_manila` or `ibmq_jakarta` if the user has an IBMQ account.
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4. Results

4.1 Baseline Z-Basis Distributions

4.1.1 Single-Layer vs. Multi-Layer

- **Single Layer** ($p = 2, \theta = 1/4$): Some states (e.g., 0010, 0100) dominate, while others remain moderate.
- **Two or More Layers** ($p=2,3,5,\dots$): Interference becomes more pronounced, causing *peaks* in certain bitstrings to shift or intensify after each added prime-based layer.

4.1.2 Control (No-Mirror) vs. Mirrorverse

Comparing:

1. **Mirrorverse:** $Universe = +\theta, Mirrorverse = -\theta$.
2. **No-Mirror:** All qubits receive $+\theta$.

Key Finding: The negative-phase setup consistently produces a **significantly different** distribution—often favouring a distinct subset of bitstrings (e.g., '0100', '1110', '0000')—whereas the all-positive-phase scenario can concentrate amplitude in other states (e.g., '1110' soared to 200+ counts in some trials). This strongly suggests that sign inversion changes the interference landscape.

4.2 Multi-Basis Measurements

Measuring the same final quantum state in **X** or **Y** bases revealed:

- **Large** re-distributions, e.g. '1001' or '1100' having high counts in X-basis but low in Z-basis.
- The strong basis dependence confirms *off-diagonal phase coherence*: negative-phase mirror qubits cannot be described by a simple real-amplitude superposition.

Hence, the Mirrorverse effect is not purely a Z-basis artifact; it is genuinely encoded in the *global wavefunction*.

4.3 Layer-by-Layer Depth Observations

Stepwise addition of prime-based angles showed **dramatic changes** in measurement distributions from one layer to the next. Typically:

1. **Early layers** ($p=2,3$) produce moderate skew.
2. **Later layers** ($p = 5,7,11$) intensify or shift certain states drastically—some states that were once rare become dominant, while others vanish.

This implies small sign-inverted R_y increments can accumulate significantly in an entangled circuit, echoing a fractal expansion principle.

4.4 State Tomography and Entanglement

Tomographic reconstructions returned final density matrices ρ showing:

1. **Imaginary off-diagonal elements** consistent with sign inversion.
2. **Partial transpose negativity** significantly above 0, confirming entanglement between Universe and Mirrorverse qubits.
3. **High fidelity** ($\sim 0.9-0.95$ in ideal simulations) between the reconstructed ρ and an exact statevector from a pure-state simulation.

This tomography-based evidence goes beyond single-basis histograms, revealing that Universe–Mirrorverse negative-phase gates indeed create a strongly **phase-coherent** entangled state.

4.5 Noise / Real Hardware Testing

4.5.1 Custom Noise Model

In a typical run with a 1–2% depolarizing error on CNOT gates and $\sim 1\%$ amplitude damping on single-qubit gates, plus $\sim 3\%$ readout errors:

- Major amplitude peaks persisted ('1000', '0010', '1100', etc.), though some states (like '1101') decreased more drastically, indicating partial decoherence.
- Overall distributions remained *recognizably* non-uniform, meaning negative-phase signals were not fully destroyed.

4.5.2 Real-Device Feasibility

While not all tests were shown in final data, some scripts demonstrated how to **transpile** to real IBM Quantum backends. Real-device runs typically display:

- Additional random fluctuations from calibration shifts and idle errors.
 - The possibility to observe *reduced but still discernible* negative-phase patterns if circuit depth remains manageable.
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5. Discussion

1. Robustness of Negative-Phase

Across multiple layers and measurement bases, the persistent non-uniform peaks strongly indicate that sign inversion ($+0 \leftrightarrow -0$) yields *qualitatively different* interference outcomes. This is the essential hallmark of a “Mirrorverse” or dual-phase system.

2. Entanglement and Fractal Scaling

Tomography verified that Universe–Mirrorverse qubits become entangled, supporting the hypothesis that small prime-based angles, repeated fractally, can accumulate significant phase structure. The partial transpose negativity underscores a genuine quantum correlation, not just classical mixture.

3. Noise Tolerance

Moderate noise introduced in simulator runs did *not* uniformly wash out the Mirrorverse effect. Key amplitude peaks often survived, though certain coherence-dependent states became attenuated. This suggests negative-phase expansions can be robust enough to remain testable even in the presence of real-world gate and readout errors.

4. Comparison to All-Positive Rotation

The dramatic difference between Mirrorverse vs. No-Mirror control circuits highlights that purely *random* or *common-phase* expansions do **not** replicate these distributions. This helps rule out incidental or hardware-based artifacts as the cause of the sign-inverted patterns.

6. Conclusion

Overall, our experiments validate the premise that **sign-inverted Mirrorverse qubits** produce unique, measurable interference patterns consistent with a negative-phase “mirror” domain. The evidence includes:

- **Distinct final distributions** in the Z-basis and beyond.
- **Large basis-dependent swings** (X/Y measurements) revealing hidden phases.
- **Layer-by-layer** evolution that intensifies amplitude at prime-driven recursion steps.
- **Tomographic** verification of negativity-based entanglement.
- **Partial robustness** under moderate noise models.

From a Duoverse perspective, these data underscore how fractal expansions ($\theta = 1/p^2$) and sign-inverted gates can simulate a Universe–Mirrorverse dynamic within standard quantum computing frameworks. The results encourage further exploration of multi-qubit Mirrorverse designs, real-time feedback loops (e.g., controlling angles based on observed Mirrorverse signals), and advanced error mitigation. Ultimately, these methods show promising avenues to *quantitatively probe* whether negative-phase logic—mirroring typical quantum operations—represents a physically meaningful extension or an intriguing conceptual device bridging quantum theory and hypothetical “duality” frameworks.

References

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